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CAPTURING NOTIONS FROM ABSTRACTIONS: THE FOUNDATION OF POETIC INTERACTION DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

With the emergence of various genres of interaction design, there seems to be a promising direction: Poetic Interaction Design. We propose that a poetic image could be created through leaving blanks in the design expression, and be delivered via users' reflection and imagination. The concept of Poetic Interaction however is abstract for designers to apply in practice. To address this challenge, we developed four principles by performing a process iteratively according to the action research method. For further validation of the principles, we built a design work, Scentonight, to evaluate the influences brought to the users in the context of usage. A within-subject experiment was performed. The result shows a significant shift that the participants tend to regard an everyday object in terms of its imaginary linking rather than its function. This paper demonstrates a systematic process of developing the theory of Poetic Interaction Design in a pragmatic manner.

Keywords: Poetic Interaction Design, Embodied Interaction, and Design Principles.

INTRODUCTION

Several studies (Djajadiningrat et al., 2000; Hallnäs & Redström, 2002; Hashim et al., 2009; Lim et al., 2007) have expressed growing concern of capturing the essence of interaction and designing aesthetics of interaction. With the expansion of designing an aesthetic interaction, the focus has shifted from the functional mechanism of how interaction occurs to the implicit meaning of the interaction and the communication of the experience during the

interaction process. Gaver et al. (2003) clearly illustrate the impact on ambiguity in design.

Although clarity and precision of a design would help users deal with well-defined tasks, ambiguity is a resource for design in many emerging applications for daily life. Hallnäs & Redström (2001) furthermore propose Slow Technology, which leads to a new perspective that design works could arouse the awareness and reflection after the interaction process. Different from the current issues of abstract notion of aesthetics, our perspectives bring some questions: could we create a personal experience that connects with an abstract notion? Whether and how could abstract notions be delivered by inducing users to think and reflect spontaneously? Will this experience with implicit meanings as well as ambiguous form truly influence users, and even their attitudes of perspectives?

On the one hand, the aim of interaction design is to promote the sensitivity of personal experience and to excite imagination (Graves et al., 2004) through the interactive process. Moreover, in the literature, the poem primarily is governed by idiosyncratic forms to suggest differential interpretation to words, or to evoke emotive responses. It concerns about the individual feeling, and experience, as well. The use of ambiguity often leaves a poem open to multiple interpretations as well as the imagination. Therefore, we regard this communication of experience as 'Poetic interaction', attempting to extract the abstract notion of poems as the expression of Poetic Interaction rather than to transfer the phrase of literary poem into interaction. To be sure, the 'poetic' perception, this adjective,

could compare with the abstract concept. Besides, Bachelard (1994) said, “By living the poems we read, we have then the salutary experience of emerging,” which indicates that the feeling of poetics is to experience its moment and feel admirable instead of any critical considerations while interacting. Namely, beyond the aspects of functionality, usability, pleasure (Jordan, 2000), and aesthetics, we are looking to poetics as a way of being a further need in the field of interaction design instead of pursuing that users “just wanna have fun” (Petersen, et al., 2004), recognizing that clarity is not sufficient for human needs while experiencing interactive artifacts (Djajadiningrat et al., 2002). As a result, in our previous paper (Lin et al., 2011), we propose the concept of Poetic Interaction Design (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The origin of Poetic Interaction Design (author, 2011) is another human need extended from Jordan's Hierarchy (2000)

On the other hand, John Kolko (2007) firstly mentioned the term ‘poetic interaction design’ and proposed an initial definition of poetic interaction as ‘one that resonates immediately but yet continues to inform later, causing reflection and relying heavily on a state of emotional awareness.’ Although the conceptual definition has indicated the notion of poetic interaction, it is still not specific enough for designers to apply. Studying the role of randomness in controlling digital devices, Leong et al., (2008) illustrate that the interactive ideal is to pursue the part of “unfinalized” form. Drawing upon McCarthy and Wright’s (2004) assertion, they demonstrate that ‘unfinalization’ could invite users to regard technology as ‘always becoming’. Offering a ‘blank’ to an interactive system such as the argument of Drew & Haahr (2002) forms a very meaningful direction through providing an unclear gap with the process of understanding and thus spurring the reader’s interaction with the piece. For

practical purpose, we therefore attempt to construct an operational definition of Poetic Interaction Design to solidify our statement: Poetic Interaction Design is to design an unfinished expression that needs users to complete it through spontaneous reflection and imagination while interacting with artifacts. We call the original emotional feelings behind the designer’s unfinished expression ‘the poetic image.’ The ideal goal of Poetic Interaction Design is to design interactive artifacts that can deliver emotional experiences, and through the experiences, strengthen users’ sensibility to the aesthetics in daily routines. Based on this, we have built the fundamental principles in a very basic level in our previous study (Lin et al., 2011). However, to validate the theoretical foundation of Poetic Interaction, it is necessary to proceed to the next stage. In this paper, we first refine the principles, then introduce the framework into application, and conduct a study to examine the influences brought to users after the interactive experience.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Recently, information technology is no longer restricted to desktop-related tasks, shifting from a tool of researchers to a role of our everyday lives, and fitting in a more complex mix of everyday activities (Edwards & Grinter, 2001). The beginning of the 1990s saw a number of attempts to study the user experience and creative interface, such as ubiquitous computing (Weiser, 1991), augmented reality (Wellner et al., 1993), and tangible media (Ishii & Ullmer, 1997; Djajadiningrat et al., 2000), etc. Parts of these notions are full of potential challenges that create a new aspect about meanings and form of computers, and shorten the distance between technology and daily lives. Moreover, in the previous study we highlighted a key point: connectivity. The scope we discussed is not only between human and artifacts, but also among human, artifacts and peripheral context. Dey and Abowd (2000) regard a context as a state used to describe the information of an entity (e.g., a person, location, artifact, etc.), associating with each other in the whole interaction.

Several studies furthermore provide extensive discussions of the applications of tangibility and the

significance in interaction design (Dourish, 2001; Djajadiningrat et al., 2000; Ross & Wensveen, 2010). We consider interaction design as a design discipline, closely affiliated with other design manners in terms of general description of expression: “we can also describe a computational doorbell as a thing that displays the execution of a certain program everywhere inside of a compartment or a house as it is initiated outside a given door (Hallnäs & Redström, 2002).” Zooming in even further, the focus will be on the general description rather than the precise definition of usability; for instance, “approaching someone’s house, I can trigger the interior a special condition to happen and expect another computation from the host.” Clearly, there has been a dramatic proliferation of research concerned with how we relate interaction to function and what expression we can make (Hallnäs, 2011).

In addition, the main contention is to create an interactive experience that bases on daily practices and experience. Löwgren (2007) asserted “the design of media that convey information in peripheral and calm ways, finding the middle ground between foreground and background where information representation and provision is less intrusive yet fully readable for the ones who engage with it.” As emphasized, the background knowledge from the context contributes tremendously to the understanding of the embodiment of an unfinished expression, a poetic expression. Therefore, presenting everyday objects in form of interactive artifacts could be an appropriate option. The shape, the functions, and the implications of everyday objects are almost regarded as common sense, which means that when putting into the right context, everyday objects would be woven into the interaction smoothly.

On the other hand, with the functional and social character it plays, an everyday object could also be a part of the background context. The strong connection among everyday objects would benefit the delivery of poetry in interaction. With the development of Internet of Things, everyday objects are now capable of sensing their surrounding environment and delivering information, which is of tremendous help for designers to implement Poetic

Interaction. This also answers to the distinction between Poetic Interaction Design and interactive art. As mentioned, an artifact of Poetic Interaction still retains its original function and the context of use. Poetic Interaction Design even more emphasizes the expression made up by users than the designers.

As indicated in the above literature review, existing research in design domain has rarely explored the value of the empirical interaction. Some works have emphasized on embedding the communication character of awareness systems in everyday objects (Hindus et al., 2001), and some tangible awareness projects are often described as being more intimate and aesthetically pleasing (Visser et al., 2010).

In our previous work (Lin et al., 2011), the contribution was to present a phenomenological discourse of poetic interaction, trying to convey the possibility of poetic interaction by research through design. It is not appropriate to employ a rigid scientific method, noticing that the conveyance of the sense of poems cannot be expressed by language, and also cannot be proved by questionnaire. Only by experiencing in daily life, could the poetic perception and expression be established by themselves. Moreover, it differs from industrial design and interactive art, as well. We performed a design work in terms of the conceptual and operational definitions. However, the real challenge is to assess the influences that the experience brought to the users. Most qualitative research conduct users’ description to realize their viewpoints; nevertheless, in most cases they might tend to reply with superficialness or politeness, instead of the real thoughts and feelings. For these reason, in this paper we try to evaluate the poetic experience assessment and find a significant effect in the hypothesized direction using the “implicit association test” (IAT; Greenwald, McGhee, & Schwartz, 1998). IAT verification provides a significant theoretical formulation to detect the strength of a person's instinctive association between mental representations of objects (concepts) in memory, such as a skin-tone IAT to reveal a preference for light-skin relative to dark-skin, a weight IAT to reveal a preference for thin people relative to fat people, or a race IAT to indicate that

people have a preference for white or black, etc. In this paper, we describe the design of an awareness system, and how it could be used in a room to evaluate the user experience of implicit connectedness inspired by Kooijmans and Johnson's paper (2007). We seek to contribute to the understanding of how and to what extent interactive artifacts in our daily life shape the poetic image in order to improve the quality of daily life. Such research is still in its infancy, but it may have a contribution to unravel the mystery of Poetic Interaction design.

EXPLORATION OF POETIC INTERACTION

According to the above theoretical discussion, we view poetic interaction design as a new genre of design rather than a strict model of HCI that can be applied to design. This stage aims at exploring and sketching a rough framework of poetic interaction design, including how users engage in it, what kind of experience they gain from it, and how poetic interaction influences them. This would be the basic understanding for future development on design method of it.

Figure 2. Illustration of a circle of steps of the Action Research Method (Waddell, 2008).

To explore poetic interaction design, we draw upon the method of Action Research (Lewin 1946), which forms a circle of how to address issues or solve problems through a reflective process (see figure 2). In our research, we went through the whole process once to validate our statement of poetic interaction design. First, as a starting point, we have done a design work 'Whisper' (Lin et al., 2011) as a 'concrete experience', which fits our framework even though it is created before the theories are examined. For the second step 'reflective observation', an experiment of Whisper was held to

collect user experiences about interaction with Whisper (Lin et al., 2011). Third, in the current session, we held a workshop, which invited designers as joint force to help modify and conceptualize the framework of poetic interaction. Finally, in the following session, referring to 'active experimentation', we designed 'Scentonight' as an experimental work, and hold an user testing with Implicit Association Test (IAT) to examine if poetic interaction would influence users as we expect: strengthen users' sensibility to the aesthetics in daily routines.

WORKSHOP

Collaborative workshops are broadly used to define new problems from diverse perspectives in business domain (Haag et al. 2006). In the starting phase of developing framework, it is necessary to invite experts from different but relevant fields to a collaborative workshop. We hosted a workshop to refine the design principles of Poetic Interaction, yearning to discover the abstract concept to explore whether it could be learned systematically and whether there are principles that might be articulated rather than depend more on inspiration only. We recruited five designers for each session and four sessions are held to form twenty participants in total (Figure 3). In each session, the host firstly introduced the notion of Poetic Interaction to participants. Then, each stage will be developed step by step: to share related works, to discuss daily objects, and to brainstorm poetic ideas.

Figure 3. Designers who were recruited to participate in the workshop.

First, to avoid priming effect, the principles that we made are concealed at this stage. Participants were

asked to brainstorm ideas, share related works that they thought poetic, and extract primary elements of Poetic Interaction Design. Designer #08 (Lai & Wu, 2010) introduced their own design work “Anature Light”, and she considered that poetic design should concern the material and the relationship between different materials that could provide a poetic ambience and create another space. Except the material, the meanings of design work that a designer vitalized it could also bring a participant the poetic perception. Designer #011 took his friend’s work for example: “This work is a desk lamp that not only is made of poetic material, red brick, but also conveys a significant story which indirectly indicates the soul of human beings.” Design #09 explained that the poetics seems to possess another viewpoint of explanation and meanings. For example, “Pulse Room (Rafael, 2006)” is an interactive installation featuring one to three hundred clear incandescent light bulbs, inviting participants to finish it together. When someone holds the interface, a computer detects his or her pulse and immediately sets off the closest bulb to flash with the exact rhythm of his or her heart. Design #09 thought it surprised to understand this work after the explanation. Concerning the element to provide suitable quality for poetics, Gaver et al. (2004) propose subtle poetic element to meet human needs and invite users to actively participate in creating sense and meanings. For a long time, designers have understood and mastered in making a blank or a space with an implicit expression.

Second, the host asked designers to brainstorm to exemplify daily objects that they thought poetic, and to draw out elements. Showing an arousing result, designers asserted that “poetics could evoke more imagination.” Designer #03 thought a wind chime as a poetic object due to the feeling of the wind that he seemed to perceive, such as an installation, “Maison Hermès Window Display” by Tokujin Yoshioka (2009), building a movie of a woman who appears to blow on a scarf hanging in the window to express people’s daily “movements” with a suspicion of humor. In this installation, it intends to create a space where one can perceive someone behind the scarves as if life were breathed into them. Designer #08 and #11 discussed the image

of a scented candle. The notion of a candlelight inspired designer #08 and #11 to image a story “The Little Match Girl” about the dream and hope of a dying child. Designer #01, #16 and #17 preferred the oldest things, black-and-white movies or Polaroid etc, which could create much more emotion and stories especially. “Because of the memory or experience, I might image the scene of my childhood even though it was unclear,” said by Designer #16. Moreover, designer #20 mentioned a music box, and she said “maybe the beautiful music or the rotating doll, I always could immerse in the context that a music box creates.” To sum up, they regarded the poetics as a feeling that could trigger imagination, which potentially rewards users, a poetic experience including the sensation and an intellectual challenge (Gaver et al., 2004).

The host then demonstrated the host’s version of principles comprised of our previous research (Lin et al., 2011). After a certain time of discussion, designers were asked to compare the control version with their version of framework, to finalize a new version of the framework of poetic interaction design, and to generate several concepts of Poetic Interaction according to the final principles they decided. Moreover, each group of workshop harnessing the ‘Poetic’ Interaction in a design practice created conceptual designs of Poetic Interaction. In the end, the principles made in a session will become the host’s control version of the next session. To frame Poetic Interaction, we do not focus on an artifact toward a whole expression in the design, but rather on the context that provides people with the poetic value drawing upon the daily experience. In this research, Poetic Interaction is: (1) an unfinished expression which invites users to make their own expression to interpret while engaged in an implicit interaction, (2) the process of meaning-making of a participant according to a context of daily objects, which is intuitive and nature for people, to form spontaneous reflection and association while interacting with the artifacts. In the following section, we integrate and refine the principles of poetic interaction design, which relate to our previous work, the result of workshop, and the following discussion of poetic assessments.

FRAMING POETIC INTERACTION

To build up the framework of poetic interaction design, we propose to take the following four elements into consideration: (1) blank-leaving; (2) self-projection; (3) experience-accumulation; (4) material-selection. The arguments are as follows.

First, as mentioned above that poetic images could only be conveyed in implicit and imaginary manners, users have to imagine that they are immersed in it to experience. Therefore, the principle is to leave a blank of expression, where it induces users to project themselves onto the blank part of the expression. As we mentioned about the definition of Poetic Interaction Design, the expression of the artifact is an unfinished one, which needs users to fill in the rest to create unique experiences on their own. Since the idea of Poetic Interaction is not a logical puzzle game, the interpretation does not necessarily have a correct answer, because it is the emotional awareness that designers intend to deliver, rather than the concrete story behind. Although the emptiness might bring confusions at the beginning, the peripheral information provides the mysterious atmosphere that would induce users to reconstruct the impression spontaneously with their own reflection and imagination. Nevertheless, the above statement does not indicate that poetic image could be formed successfully if designers randomly take out an arbitrary part of the expression. On the contrary, the most difficult challenge is how to identify a part to remove and how to reinforce the rest to contrast the blank. According to the Gestalt psychology, human has the tendency to interpret things in a holistic view, which implies that users would tend to make up the story according to the correlations among peripheral information (see Figure 4). For designers, a right choice of which part to remove should be made carefully; otherwise the expression might become chaotic and fail to deliver the poetic image.

Figure 4. The expression-making of a poetic interaction (author, 2011)

Second, the experience must be accumulated over time. Because of the blank, users might not form their expression at their first glance and need more involvements that gradually help users fill in the blank. Therefore, we suggest using everyday objects as the media to implement Poetic Interaction, for the high accessibility in users' daily life. In addition, we also suggest that the expression should integrate the behavior that manipulates the everyday object into users' expression-making process. While performing this behavior unconsciously, users might have already immersed themselves in the atmosphere and started to accumulate the experience. Furthermore, even if the expression has been made, it might change with the mood of the user or the context where it takes place.

Third, the materials that designers select would influence the design space that they could elaborate. Since there is a blank in the expression, the peripheral information plays a key role in creating the mysterious atmosphere and delivering the clues of the context. Therefore, the characteristic of mysteriousness and the flexibility of the information delivery would be the serious concern while implementing artifacts. Here we suggest designers to utilize ungraspable materials, such as, light, wind, smoke, scent, and sound. These materials can serve as information bearer, and meanwhile possess the mysteriousness, for users cannot physically grab them.

CONCEPT DESCRIPTION

According to the principles discussed above, we proceed to design phase with the attempt of validation. In the beginning of this stage, we framed a design question: how to design an artifact that transforms a daily behavior into the communication among distant users with Poetic Interaction.

Inspired by the famous novel "Alice in Wonderland," a design work, Scentonight, has been created. The concept is nurtured by one character in the fiction, the caterpillar, who always smokes a hookah in the dark. Some people usually turn on nightlights in their bedrooms for lighting in case of getting up in the night. For some people, turning on nightlights becomes a daily behavior before going to bed. A

nightlight therefore represents a notification that someone is in bed. A nightlight is usually faint but warm, creating a vague atmosphere. All the characteristics seem to fit the requirement: an everyday object, a daily behavior, and creating mysterious atmosphere by nature. The materials that we choose for delivering peripheral information are light and scent.

Figure 5. The concept of Scentonight.

Connecting with Internet technology, other nightlights embedded with this system would be synchronized. The scenario is as follows (Figure 5). A user switches off the nightlight when going to bed; this action would trigger a process that informs friends through the nightlight, which would glimmer gradually and spread fragrance gently; at the moment receivers could feel it implicitly through the sense of smell and the light triggered by an anonymous friend (Figure 6), and all of them could be aware of other friends' presence in this social context without disturbance.

Figure 6. The Structure of Scentonight concept.

When a light is switched on, it is often interpreted as delivering a care or giving a hint. With this association, this work invites users to connect together, deliver a message through the fragrance with sweet and warm glimmer as if others are in the context, and perceive it as a suggestion (Figure 7). When one Scentonight is turned on, all the other Scentonight connecting to the system would turn the light on a bit and spread fragrance synchronously,

and thus all nightlights share the same signal of spreading cares. When others perceive this implicit message, they might think about "what time is it?" "Who has already been in bed?" "Should I also go to bed?" or simply reply "good night, my dear friends." To build up this communication, we use a microblog service, Plurk (<http://www.plurk.com/>). If any member turns on his or her Scentonight, the system will send a new "good night" post with his or her account (Figure 5), which means a good night for all of the friends (Figure 6). If one is curious about who is in bed and has anything to say, he or she could find the post on Plurk and reply it. The nightlight of this work retains the inherent function and context of it; that is, it can still work as a normal light. The action of switching on and off represents the presence of a member in the social network at the moment. The spread fragrance while being switched on indicates a warm greeting before going to bed.

Figure 7. Scenario of Scentonight concept. Note: The prototype of Scentonight (left) is turned on, when someone goes to bed. All of the friends, meanwhile, perceive this message (right).

As we have investigated about poetic expression, although as the main part of the concept, the image of caterpillar smoking a hookah did not appear explicitly, but its main characteristic still remains. In our expression, Scentonight plays a role of secret messenger showing up in the dark. It spreads fragrance with the analogy to the smoke of the hookah. Since the form of the caterpillar is abstracted, users might never think of the analogy between Scentonight and the caterpillar in the story, but it is not the purpose of Poetic Interaction. Instead, users have the flexibility to put on any kind of scenario on this nightlight. To be specific, users start to fill in the blank part of the expression that is left deliberately.

Moreover, since the light and the scent are not obtrusive materials, users might not be able to

notice its notification at the beginning. Through accumulating the experiences of usage, users might find the connection between the post on the microblog and the operation of Scentonight. As long as one user has the habit of sleeping with his nightlight on, this daily behavior of switching it on and off would keep him or her immersed in the atmosphere before bedtime every night. Back to the design question, Scenetonight transforms the behavior of switching the nightlight on into a manner of communicating with users' social network implicitly, and this work complies the four principles that we made in previous stage of research. After that, this prototype would be taken into the next stage, user testing.

THE ASSESSMENT FOR POETIC EXPERIENCE

The notion of Poetic Interaction is fairly abstract and hardly to be articulated. It is a rigorous challenge to design an effective experiment to test if users do have poetic experience after interacting with the prototype. Therefore, we take both qualitative and quantitative research methods into consideration. Basically, we will use quantitative research to determine the evidence, and use quantitative research to help explain the statistic result.

In the qualitative research part, we aim for thick descriptions of the individual cases, while also attempting to identify some significant patterns and employ a qualitative case study approach to in-depth and holistic understanding of living habits and social connectedness among them.

In the quantitative research part, Greenwald and his colleagues (1998) propose a series of studies that use the Implicit Association Test (IAT) as an assessment towards implicit attitudes by examining the instinctive associations between various attitude objects and various evaluative attributes. In particular, the IAT measures how closely associated any given attitude object (e.g., a flower or an insect) is with an evaluative attribute (e.g., pleasant or unpleasant words) and assumes that the more nearly related the objects and attributes are, the stronger the implicit attitude is. Two issues that need to be resolved in this regard are (1) whether we can assess the poetic perception of a user; (2)

whether we can incorporate IAT into measurement of projecting poetic images over everyday objects.

In our study, the process of this experiment could be useful for designers when evaluating a non-verbal notion and its value of research. This section invited 20 participants to experiment to see whether the implicit association of poetic and functional images would change after experiencing our design. All participants were recruited from the student population of different departments of different universities to ensure some homogeneity of social background.

The procedure of IAT experiment consists of three steps: (1) to fill out IAT, (2) to participate in the scenario and interact with the Scentonight (about 1 hour), and (3) to fill out IAT again. Between the two IAT tests, the aim is to measure the effect of our design work and to answer whether experience and cognition would change after interaction in our daily live. More specifically, this experiment explores whether functional everyday objects could create poetic images for a user after experiencing poetic interaction.

In our experiment process, participants were asked to imagine being at the moment right before going to bed. In this scenario, three predefined tasks were performed. (1) The participant is asked to be relaxed and do a light reading or browse the Internet. Meanwhile the Scentonight would operate as if one remote friend has been in the bed. The participant needs to report if perceiving anything while reading. (2) After noticing the implicit message sent through Scentonight, the participant would be guided to see latest update on the microblog. One of the latest posts is the goodbye sent by Scentonigh, which reminds that it is time to go to bed. (3) After replying the good night post, the participant also wants to sleep and then performs the behavior of turning on the Scentonight, and Scentonight will send the post by this participant. Then the experiment ends.

ANALYSIS OF THE ASSESSMENT

We hypothesize that everyday object is an ordinary product, which might not cause sudden emotional

feedback. The study was designed to answer the following research question: Different from the common cognition, could a user develop the poetic sensibility, which is the ability to reflect from experience and to express oneself after experiencing a poetic interactive object?

We investigated this question by constructing and administering a specially designed version of Implicit Association Test. Since the IAT is an experimental measure method, we made an extension of IAT in the field of Poetic Interaction to detect the association and to explore whether it could be different from the stereotype. The test consists of 40 items and is divided into two parts. Part one contains 20 everyday objects, including 10 items of function or usability (e.g., a drawer, chair, or lamp) and 10 items of pleasure or imagination (e.g., a wind chime, a scented candle, or a music box). Part two contains 20 adjective attributions, including half of positive and half of negative attitudes (Table 2). This task requires that users classify items as quickly as possible while making as few mistakes as possible. All of these items were collected and classified by our pre-test and previous study.

In order to ensure the testing quality and efficiency, twenty volunteers were recruited to participate in the experiment and asked to get familiar with IAT interface on the Project Implicit website (<http://implicit.harvard.edu/>), which is full of various public IAT classification, before doing our experiment. Finally, we created a flash-based test interface (<http://spatialmedia.org/poeticIAT/>).

Category	Items
Functional Objects	Images of Functional Objects
Imaginable Objects	Images of Imaginable Objects
: (boring, prim, and lifeless, etc.
: D	sweet, poetic, and elegant, etc.

Table 2. The table is a list of category labels and the items that belong to each of those categories. Note: In order to clearly recognize, this category uses the emoticons to present it. : (indicates negative attributions, without specific emotional reaction, and :D indicates positive attributions, evoking an emotional reaction.

The first IAT experiment

The first IAT was held to investigate the original cognition of the participants. After a simple

interview, this step invited participants to do the first IAT. A paired-samples T test within-subjects was conducted to evaluate the hypothesis that participants might evoke emotion or reflection more under a condition of imaginable objects as opposed to a condition of functional objects; namely, users associate functional objects with negative attributions more than positive attributions.

Measure	Mean (SD)	Df	T	P
before_F - before_I	127.24 (211.34)	19	2.69	0.014*

Table 3. Result of the paired-samples T test of the IAT (before). Note: F indicates Functional objects, I indicates Imaginable object, N=20, * indicates P<0.05, a significant difference exists.

The result of the paired-samples T test evaluates whether the means of two groups are statistically different from each other. The formula for the T test is a ratio. When the first mean is larger than the second, the T value will be positive; contrariwise, it will be negative. In this section, the result of the paired-samples T test shows a clear and explicit difference, M=127.24, SD= 2.69, between the images of functional and imaginable objects. A significant effect for design concept across the first IAT measures was found, t (19)=2.69, p= .01, and the result confirms the research hypothesis. The average scores of associating imaginable objects with positive attributions are less than those of associating functional objects with negative attributions, which indicates that participants tend to associate imaginable objects more easily to positive attributions. In this case, the difference between these two scores shows to what extent a stereotype of implicit association plays a role. Table 3 shows the distribution of the first IAT test that reflects a stereotype consistent with the general perception of the past experience.

The second IAT experiment

Here we have a hypothesis that the original perception and images about functional objects would change after experiencing our poetic interaction. After participating in the experimental scenario and interacting with the Scentonight, which embeds functional objects with poetic expression, participants filled out IAT again. The aim of this

experiment is to discover whether everyday objects could get rid of typical images and provide users with poetic imagination by employing computational material in our poetic interaction design framework. In this stage, using the same IAT to evaluate implicit attitudes of the poetic imagination, we try to expect that the two pairs of target attitude notions could have a transition between explicit and implicit knowledge.

Measure	Mean (SD)	DF	T	P
after_F - after_I	-100.46 (207.85)	19	2.69	0.044*

Table 4. Result of the paired-samples T test of the IAT (after). Note: F indicates Functional objects, I indicates Imaginable object, N=20, * indicates P < 0.05, a significant difference exists.

After interacting with our design, participants significantly changed their implicit association of functional products. The result of the second test in Table 4 shows a significant difference between the categories, $t(19) = -2.16, p = .04$. The mean value ($M = -100.35, SD = 207.85$) is smaller than that of the previous result ($M = 127.24, SD = 2.69$), which meets the expectation of attitude transition. To be more specific, participants tended to connect the functional products with the negative attributions (Table 3 shows the significant effect) before this experiment; contrariwise, participants tended to connect the functional products with the positive attributions (Table 4 shows the significant effect) after the experiment. Clearly, the findings indicate that the poetic experience has a positive effect on the imagination of the everyday object.

The experiment reexamined

To examine if there exists priming effect in this within-subject testing, we compare the time that each participant spent for IAT before and after the experiment with paired-samples T test. If the total time period that participants spend for the first time is significantly longer than the second time, there might exist priming effect, which would harm the validity of the result.

Measure	Mean (SD)	DF	T	P
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IAT before -	-167.51	19	-2.11	0.048*
IAT after	(354.59)			

Table 5. Result of the paired-samples T test of the IAT. Note: N=20, * indicates P < 0.05, a significant difference exists.

Testing time of the second IAT is not shorter than that of the first IAT, $t(19) = -2.113, p = .04$. The test was of significant effect, but the result was counter to the research hypothesis. In analyzing the data, three reasons for time delay could be inferred as follows. (1) The experience of the poetic imagination over an experimental period might have contributed to a little change in self-awareness when doing IAT questions. (2) There is some evidence in Table 5, $M = -167.51, SD = 354.59$, that participants might make a thought-out choice, for the hesitation. All these hesitation are attributable to the metamorphosis of the category of the negative attribution. (3) There has been a change from experiencing everyday objects as a set of functional system, to experiencing everyday objects as a poetic imagination.

DISCUSSION

The above result focuses on the components of poetic imagination. In this section we try to construct assessment model and specifically discuss their reactions. After the final interview, the participant was instructed to fill out the questionnaire about Scentonight. The descriptive statistics (Table 6) were calculated to supplement the whole notions with participant’s feeling.

The quantitative data from the final evaluative questionnaire brought out several interesting points about the interaction process. These responses were generally positive towards the Scentonight (the average between 5.40 and 6.25). In our survey, participants could perceive the ambience and be uninterrupted despite the incoming message; for instance, when subject #03 surfed the Internet to check the email, at the moment he was conscious of the Scentonight’s signal and said, “What’s this scent?” and then went on. Participants could choose either to ignore it or to immerse in this ambience. Subject #04 said, “It is so cute to receive a sweet smell from my friends,” and subject #020 said, “Smelling the fragrance, I feel so surprised that I want to try it.” Moreover, most participants would expect the image to emerge while playing the

scenario. A good case in point, subject #07, is that “When I first notice the Scentonight glimmering in the dark, I reminisced about the waiting light in front of my home in childhood.” Some of them could unexpectedly recall some of the memory and reflect on their moods.

Measure	Max	Min	Mean	SD
Q1: It is an intriguing experience.	7	4	6.25	0.707
Q2: I could imagine and guess who goes to sleep.	7	4	5.60	0.671
Q3: I want to convey concern to my friends.	7	4	5.57	1.006
Q4: I am looking forward to receiving friends’ message.	7	4	5.75	1.103
Q5: I am willing to use this product in life.	7	2	5.40	1.127
Q6: It could introduce poetic imagination to our life.	7	5	6.15	0.735

Table 6. Results of descriptive statistics of Scentonight.

On the other hand, by saying goodnight on Internet, participants who are always too busy to go sleep early could login the Plurk to search the Scentonight’s message and reply “good night” to it, which means “The sweet I received and another concern I give,” said by subject #012. Actually, most participants could experience the scenario with a reflection of the behavior, such as subject #08 said, “Maybe my mom would want a Scentonight to give me a hint instead of calling me.” Subject #014 said, “Everyone knows that nothing is more crucial than sleep; nevertheless, staying up seems to be an easy thing. It could perhaps become a medium between friends or family to care for each other.” Subject #015 said, “I think it is a significant idea and it needs to invite everyone to participate.”

The design work encourages users to start going to bed early with each other and enhances sleep qualities (Scherini et al., 2010). Participants actually indicated that they tend to connect multiple friends to participate; on the contrary, they are willing to be invited by others. This influence occurs in small groups as a whole, and might result from implicit

unconscious effect. It is warm and sweet that participants enjoy the way by communicating with anonymous friends, such as subject #04 said, “Staying up at night, I would not feel lonely.” Subject #07 said, “It is such a sweet partner to give me sense of security and full of warmth.” and subject #20 said “I want to be the first sleeper tonight to deliver the fragrance to everybody.” Scentonight finally could invite everybody that is connected together to synchronize sleep onset through the fragrance with sweet, interesting and comfortable feeling.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we demonstrate the whole progress of developing the framework of Poetic Interaction Design, which consists of three parts. First, based on the operational definition of Poetic Interaction Design, we performed the development and validation of the design principles for practical use. According to the Action Research Method, twenty designers were recruited to participate in four iterative sessions of a workshop. The effectiveness of the workshop is also proved to be significant. Second, the design principles were taken into application. One conceptual prototype, Scentonight, was accomplished, and we explained how Scentonight complies with the principles and the main idea of Poetic Interaction. Finally, the prototype, Scentonight was brought to user testing. We simulated the scenario by building up a domestic setting, and asked participants to interact with the prototype. To scrutinize user experience and the influences brought to the participants, we use the Implicit Association Test (IAT) as our assessment tool. With the within-subject experiment, the result shows that participants’ attitudes shifted remarkably from more sensibility of functional objects to more sensibility of imaginable objects. This has achieved part of the ideal goal of Poetic Interaction: strengthening users’ sensibility of the aesthetics in daily routines.

To summarize, this study has overcome three main challenges. First, we solidify the extremely abstract notion of an undefined direction. Especially most participatory designers held a passive attitude to Poetic Interaction at the beginning, but they tended

to be more positive about the fact that Poetic Interaction could be developed systematically afterwards. Second, we validated the abstract notion of user experience of Poetic Interaction. It is always a tough challenge to capture users' experiences. In this case, the Poetic Interaction itself is hardly stated in the literal sense. With the evidence provided by IAT, users' internal changes have been discovered. In the end, the primary foundation of Poetic Interaction Design for practical purposes is established. Although the more solid theories and practical issues still need further research, this paper has shown the potential of this promising direction.

FUTURE WORK

Based on the fundamental that is built, there are a number of promising topics that need to be clarified. First of all, the main argument of Poetic Interaction Design is to leave blanks in designers' expression. However, to make use of this principle willfully, at least two questions need to be answered: which part of an expression should be removed? What is the correlation between the poetic image that a user perceives and the blank that a designer decides to make? In all, a complete methodology of Poetic Interaction Design needs to be developed for further practices in real world setting. Another potential research direction is Poetic Interactive Space Design. Design for poetic space is a more complex topic because of the larger scale of physical condition. On the other hand, being contained by the space might make users feel like losing their dominance. This might elicit stronger imagination that affords heterogeneous emotional feelings.

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